

The Forcing Weak Edge Detour Number of a Graph

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Abstract: For two vertices u and v in a graph $G = (V, E)$, the *distance* $d(u, v)$ and *detour distance* $D(u, v)$ are the length of a shortest or longest $u - v$ path in G , respectively, and the *Smarandache distance* $d_S^i(u, v)$ is the length $d(u, v) + i(u, v)$ of a $u - v$ path in G , where $0 \leq i(u, v) \leq D(u, v) - d(u, v)$. A $u - v$ path of length $d_S^i(u, v)$, if it exists, is called a *Smarandachely $u - v$ i -detour*. A set $S \subseteq V$ is called a *Smarandachely i -detour set* if every edge in G has both its ends in S or it lies on a Smarandachely i -detour joining a pair of vertices in S . In particular, if $i(u, v) = 0$, then $d_S^i(u, v) = d(u, v)$; and if $i(u, v) = D(u, v) - d(u, v)$, then $d_S^i(u, v) = D(u, v)$. For $i(u, v) = D(u, v) - d(u, v)$, such a Smarandachely i -detour set is called a *weak edge detour set* in G . The *weak edge detour number* $dn_w(G)$ of G is the minimum order of its weak edge detour sets and any weak edge detour set of order $dn_w(G)$ is a *weak edge detour basis* of G . For any weak edge detour basis S of G , a subset $T \subseteq S$ is called a *forcing subset* for S if S is the unique weak edge detour basis containing T . A forcing subset for S of minimum cardinality is a *minimum forcing subset* of S . The *forcing weak edge detour number* of S , denoted by $fdn_w(S)$, is the cardinality of a minimum forcing subset for S . The *forcing weak edge detour number* of G , denoted by $fdn_w(G)$, is $fdn_w(G) = \min\{fdn_w(S)\}$, where the minimum is taken over all weak edge detour bases S in G . The forcing weak edge detour numbers of certain classes of graphs are determined. It is proved that for each pair a, b of integers with $0 \leq a \leq b$ and $b \geq 2$, there is a connected graph G with $fdn_w(G) = a$ and $dn_w(G) = b$.

Key Words: Smarandache distance, Smarandachely i -detour set, weak edge detour set, weak edge detour number, forcing weak edge detour number.

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§1. Introduction

For vertices u and v in a connected graph G , the *distance* $d(u, v)$ is the length of a shortest $u - v$ path in G . A $u - v$ path of length $d(u, v)$ is called a $u - v$ *geodesic*. For a vertex v of G , the *eccentricity* $e(v)$ is the distance between v and a vertex farthest from v . The minimum eccentricity among the vertices of G is the *radius*, $radG$ and the maximum eccentricity among the vertices of G is its *diameter*, $diamG$ of G . Two vertices u and v of G are *antipodal* if $d(u, v)$

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$= \text{diam}G$. For vertices u and v in a connected graph G , the *detour distance* $D(u, v)$ is the length of a longest u - v path in G . A u - v path of length $D(u, v)$ is called a u - v *detour*. It is known that the distance and the detour distance are metrics on the vertex set $V(G)$. The *detour eccentricity* $e_D(v)$ of a vertex v in G is the maximum detour distance from v to a vertex of G . The *detour radius*, $\text{rad}_D G$ of G is the minimum detour eccentricity among the vertices of G , while the *detour diameter*, $\text{diam}_D G$ of G is the maximum detour eccentricity among the vertices of G . These concepts were studied by Chartrand et al. [2].

A vertex x is said to lie on a u - v detour P if x is a vertex of P including the vertices u and v . A set $S \subseteq V$ is called a *detour set* if every vertex v in G lies on a detour joining a pair of vertices of S . The *detour number* $dn(G)$ of G is the minimum order of a detour set and any detour set of order $dn(G)$ is called a *detour basis* of G . A vertex v that belongs to every detour basis of G is a *detour vertex* in G . If G has a unique detour basis S , then every vertex in S is a detour vertex in G . These concepts were studied by Chartrand et al. [3].

In general, there are graphs G for which there exist edges which do not lie on a detour joining any pair of vertices of V . For the graph G given in Figure 1.1, the edge $v_1 v_2$ does not lie on a detour joining any pair of vertices of V . This motivated us to introduce the concept of *weak edge detour set* of a graph [5].

Figure 1: G

The *Smarandache distance* $d_S^i(u, v)$ is the length $d(u, v) + i(u, v)$ of a $u - v$ path in G , where $0 \leq i(u, v) \leq D(u, v) - d(u, v)$. A $u - v$ path of length $d_S^i(u, v)$, if it exists, is called a *Smarandachely $u - v$ i -detour*. A set $S \subseteq V$ is called a *Smarandachely i -detour set* if every edge in G has both its ends in S or it lies on a Smarandachely i -detour joining a pair of vertices in S . In particular, if $i(u, v) = 0$, then $d_S^i(u, v) = d(u, v)$ and if $i(u, v) = D(u, v) - d(u, v)$, then $d_S^i(u, v) = D(u, v)$. For $i(u, v) = D(u, v) - d(u, v)$, such a Smarandachely i -detour set is called a *weak edge detour set* in G . The *weak edge detour number* $dn_w(G)$ of G is the minimum order of its weak edge detour sets and any weak edge detour set of order $dn_w(G)$ is called a *weak edge detour basis* of G . A vertex v in a graph G is a *weak edge detour vertex* if v belongs to every weak edge detour basis of G . If G has a unique weak edge detour basis S , then every vertex in S is a weak edge detour vertex of G . These concepts were studied by A. P. Santhakumaran and S. Athisayanathan [5].

To illustrate these concepts, we consider the graph G given in Figure 1.2. The sets $S_1 = \{u, x\}$, $S_2 = \{u, y\}$ and $S_3 = \{u, z\}$ are the detour bases of G so that $dn(G) = 2$ and the sets $S_4 = \{u, v, y\}$ and $S_5 = \{u, x, z\}$ are the weak edge detour bases of G so that $dn_w(G) = 3$. The vertex u is a detour vertex and also a weak edge detour vertex of G .

Figure 2: G

The following theorems are used in the sequel.

Theorem 1.1([5]) *For any graph G of order $p \geq 2$, $2 \leq dn_w(G) \leq p$.*

Theorem 1.2([5]) *Every end-vertex of a non-trivial connected graph G belongs to every weak edge detour set of G . Also if the set S of all end-vertices of G is a weak edge detour set, then S is the unique weak edge detour basis for G .*

Theorem 1.3([5]) *If T is a tree with k end-vertices, then $dn_w(T) = k$.*

Theorem 1.4([5]) *Let G be a connected graph with cut-vertices and S a weak edge detour set of G . Then for any cut-vertex v of G , every component of $G - v$ contains an element of S .*

Throughout this paper G denotes a connected graph with at least two vertices.

§2. Forcing Weak Edge Detour Number of a Graph

First we determine the weak edge detour numbers of some standard classes of graphs so that their forcing weak edge detour numbers will be determined.

Theorem 2.1 *Let G be the complete graph K_p ($p \geq 3$) or the complete bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$ ($2 \leq m \leq n$). Then a set $S \subseteq V$ is a weak edge detour basis of G if and only if S consists of any two vertices of G .*

Proof Let G be the complete graph K_p ($p \geq 3$) and $S = \{u, v\}$ be any set of two vertices of G . It is clear that $D(u, v) = p - 1$. Let $xy \in E$. If $xy = uv$, then both its ends are in S . Let $xy \neq uv$. If $x \neq u$ and $y \neq v$, then the edge xy lies on the u - v detour $P : u, x, y, \dots, v$ of length $p - 1$. If $x = u$ and $y \neq v$, then the edge xy lies on the u - v detour $P : u = x, y, \dots, v$ of length $p - 1$. Hence S is a weak edge detour set of G . Since $|S| = 2$, S is a weak edge detour basis of G .

Now, let S be a weak edge detour basis of G . Let S' be any set consisting of two vertices of G . Then as in the first part of this theorem S' is a weak edge detour basis of G . Hence $|S| = |S'| = 2$ and it follows that S consists of any two vertices of G .

Let G be the complete bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$ ($2 \leq m \leq n$). Let X and Y be the bipartite sets of G with $|X| = m$ and $|Y| = n$. Let $S = \{u, v\}$ be any set of two vertices of G .

Case 1 Let $u \in X$ and $v \in Y$. It is clear that $D(u, v) = 2m - 1$. Let $xy \in E$. If $xy = uv$, then

both of its ends are in S . Let $xy \neq uv$ be such that $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$. If $x \neq u$ and $y \neq v$, then the edge xy lies on the u - v detour $P : u, y, x, \dots, v$ of length $2m - 1$. If $x = u$ and $y \neq v$, then the edge xy lies on the u - v detour $P : u = x, y, \dots, v$ of length $2m - 1$. Hence S is a weak edge detour set of G .

Case 2 Let $u, v \in X$. It is clear that $D(u, v) = 2m - 2$. Let $xy \in E$ be such that $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$. If $x \neq u$, then the edge xy lies on the u - v detour $P : u, y, x, \dots, v$ of length $2m - 2$. If $x = u$, then the edge xy lies on the u - v detour $P : u = x, y, \dots, v$ of length $2m - 2$. Hence S is a weak edge detour set of G .

Case 3 Let $u, v \in Y$. It is clear that $D(u, v) = 2m$. Then, as in Case 2, S is a weak edge detour set of G . Since $|S| = 2$, it follows that S is a weak edge detour basis of G .

Now, let S be a weak edge detour basis of G . Let S' be any set consisting of two vertices of G . Then as in the first part of the proof of $K_{m,n}$, S' is a weak edge detour basis of G . Hence $|S| = |S'| = 2$ and it follows that S consists of any two vertices adjacent or not. \square

Theorem 2.2 *Let G be an odd cycle of order $p \geq 3$. Then a set $S \subseteq V$ is a weak edge detour basis of G if and only if S consists of any two adjacent vertices of G .*

Proof Let $S = \{u, v\}$ be any set of two adjacent vertices of G . It is clear that $D(u, v) = p - 1$. Then every edge $e \neq uv$ of G lies on the u - v detour and both the ends of the edge uv belong to S so that S is a weak edge detour set of G . Since $|S| = 2$, S is a weak edge detour basis of G .

Now, assume that S is a weak edge detour basis of G . Let S' be any set of two adjacent vertices of G . Then as in the first part of this theorem S' is a weak edge detour basis of G . Hence $|S| = |S'| = 2$. Let $S = \{u, v\}$. If u and v are not adjacent, then since G is an odd cycle, the edges of u - v geodesic do not lie on the u - v detour in G so that S is not a weak edge detour set of G , which is a contradiction. Thus S consists of any two adjacent vertices of G . \square

Theorem 2.3 *Let G be an even cycle of order $p \geq 4$. Then a set $S \subseteq V$ is a weak edge detour basis of G if and only if S consists of any two adjacent vertices or two antipodal vertices of G .*

Proof Let $S = \{u, v\}$ be any set of two vertices of G . If u and v are adjacent, then $D(u, v) = p - 1$ and every edge $e \neq uv$ of G lies on the u - v detour and both the ends of the edge uv belong to S . If u and v are antipodal, then $D(u, v) = p/2$ and every edge e of G lies on a u - v detour in G . Thus S is a weak edge detour set of G . Since $|S| = 2$, S is a weak edge detour basis of G .

Now, assume that S is a weak edge detour basis of G . Let S' be any set of two adjacent vertices or two antipodal vertices of G . Then as in the first part of this theorem S' is a weak edge detour basis of G . Hence $|S| = |S'| = 2$. Let $S = \{u, v\}$. If u and v are not adjacent and u and v are not antipodal, then the edges of the u - v geodesic do not lie on the u - v detour in G so that S is not a weak edge detour set of G , which is a contradiction. Thus S consists of any two adjacent vertices or two antipodal vertices of G . \square

Corollary 2.4 *If G is the complete graph K_p ($p \geq 3$) or the complete bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$ ($2 \leq m \leq n$) or the cycle C_p ($p \geq 3$), then $dn_w(G) = 2$.*

Proof This follows from Theorems 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3. \square

Every connected graph contains a weak edge detour basis and some connected graphs may contain several weak edge detour bases. For each weak edge detour basis S in a connected graph G , there is always some subset T of S that uniquely determines S as the weak edge detour basis containing T . We call such subsets "forcing subsets" and we discuss their properties in this section.

Definition 2.5 Let G be a connected graph and S a weak edge detour basis of G . A subset $T \subseteq S$ is called a forcing subset for S if S is the unique weak edge detour basis containing T . A forcing subset for S of minimum cardinality is a minimum forcing subset of S . The forcing weak edge detour number of S , denoted by $fdn_w(S)$, is the cardinality of a minimum forcing subset for S . The forcing weak edge detour number of G , denoted by $fdn_w(G)$, is $fdn_w(G) = \min \{fdn_w(S)\}$, where the minimum is taken over all weak edge detour bases S in G .

Example 2.6 For the graph G given in Figure 2.1(a), $S = \{u, v, w\}$ is the unique weak edge detour basis so that $fdn_w(G) = 0$. For the graph G given in Figure 2.1(b), $S_1 = \{u, v, x\}$, $S_2 = \{u, v, y\}$ and $S_3 = \{u, v, w\}$ are the only weak edge detour bases so that $fdn_w(G) = 1$. For the graph G given in Figure 2.1(c), $S_4 = \{u, w, x\}$, $S_5 = \{u, w, y\}$, $S_6 = \{v, w, x\}$ and $S_7 = \{v, w, y\}$ are the four weak edge detour bases so that $fdn_w(G) = 2$.

Figure 3: G

The following theorem is clear from the definitions of weak edge detour number and forcing weak edge detour number of a connected graph G .

Theorem 2.7 For every connected graph G , $0 \leq fdn_w(G) \leq dn_w(G)$.

Remark 2.8 The bounds in Theorem 2.7 are sharp. For the graph G given in Figure 2.1(a), $fdn_w(G) = 0$. For the cycle C_3 , $fdn_w(C_3) = dn_w(C_3) = 2$. Also, all the inequalities in Theorem 2.7 can be strict. For the graph G given in Figure 2.1(b), $fdn_w(G) = 1$ and $dn_w(G) = 3$ so that $0 < fdn_w(G) < dn_w(G)$.

The following two theorems are easy consequences of the definitions of the weak edge detour number and the forcing weak edge detour number of a connected graph.

Theorem 2.9 Let G be a connected graph. Then

- a) $fdn_w(G) = 0$ if and only if G has a unique weak edge detour basis,

- b) $fdn_w(G) = 1$ if and only if G has at least two weak edge detour bases, one of which is a unique weak edge detour basis containing one of its elements, and
- c) $fdn_w(G) = dn_w(G)$ if and only if no weak edge detour basis of G is the unique weak edge detour basis containing any of its proper subsets.

Theorem 2.10 Let G be a connected graph and let \mathcal{F} be the set of relative complements of the minimum forcing subsets in their respective weak edge detour bases in G . Then $\bigcap_{F \in \mathcal{F}} F$ is the set of weak edge detour vertices of G . In particular, if S is a weak edge detour basis of G , then no weak edge detour vertex of G belongs to any minimum forcing subset of S .

Theorem 2.11 Let G be a connected graph and W be the set of all weak edge detour vertices of G . Then $fdn_w(G) \leq dn_w(G) - |W|$.

Proof Let S be any weak edge detour basis S of G . Then $dn_w(G) = |S|$, $W \subseteq S$ and S is the unique weak edge detour basis containing $S - W$. Thus $fdn_w(S) \leq |S - W| = |S| - |W| = dn_w(G) - |W|$. \square

Remark 2.12 The bound in Theorem 2.11 is sharp. For the graph G given in Figure 2.1(c), $dn_w(G) = 3$, $|W| = 1$ and $fdn_w(G) = 2$ as in Example 2.6. Also, the inequality in Theorem 2.11 can be strict. For the graph G given in Figure 2.2, the sets $S_1 = \{v_1, v_4\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_2, v_3\}$ are the two weak edge detour bases for G and $W = \emptyset$ so that $dn_w(G) = 2$, $|W| = 0$ and $fdn_w(G) = 1$. Thus $fdn_w(G) < dn_w(G) - |W|$.

Figure 4: G

In the following we determine $fdn_w(G)$ for certain graphs G .

- Theorem 2.13** a) If G is the complete graph K_p ($p \geq 3$) or the complete bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$ ($2 \leq m \leq n$), then $dn_w(G) = fdn_w(G) = 2$.
- b) If G is the cycle C_p ($p \geq 4$), then $dn_w(G) = fdn_w(G) = 2$.
- c) If G is a tree of order $p \geq 2$ with k end-vertices, then $dn_w(G) = k$, $fdn_w(G) = 0$.

Proof a) By Theorem 2.1, a set S of vertices is a weak edge detour basis if and only if S consists of any two vertices of G . For each vertex v in G there are two or more vertices adjacent with v . Thus the vertex v belongs to more than one weak edge detour basis of G . Hence it follows that no set consisting of a single vertex is a forcing subset for any weak edge detour basis of G . Thus the result follows.

b) By Theorems 2.2 and 2.3, a set S of two adjacent vertices of G is a weak edge detour basis of G . For each vertex v in G there are two vertices adjacent with v . Thus the vertex v

belongs to more than one weak edge detour basis of G . Hence it follows that no set consisting of a single vertex is a forcing subset for any weak edge detour basis of G . Thus the result follows.

c) By Theorem 1.3, $dn_w(G) = k$. Since the set of all end-vertices of a tree is the unique weak edge detour basis, the result follows from Theorem 2.9(a). \square

The following theorem gives a realization result.

Theorem 2.14 *For each pair a, b of integers with $0 \leq a \leq b$ and $b \geq 2$, there is a connected graph G with $fdn_w(G) = a$ and $dn_w(G) = b$.*

Proof The proof is divided into two cases following.

Case 1: $a = 0$. For each $b \geq 2$, let G be a tree with b end-vertices. Then $fdn_w(G) = 0$ and $dn_w(G) = b$ by Theorem 2.13(c).

Case 2: $a \geq 1$. For each i ($1 \leq i \leq a$), let $F_i : u_i, v_i, w_i, x_i, u_i$ be the cycle of order 4 and let $H = K_{1,b-a}$ be the star at v whose set of end-vertices is $\{z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{b-a}\}$. Let G be the graph obtained by joining the central vertex v of H to both vertices u_i, w_i of each F_i ($1 \leq i \leq a$). Clearly the graph G is connected and is shown in Figure 2.3.

Let $W = \{z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{b-a}\}$ be the set of all $(b - a)$ end-vertices of G . First, we show that $dn_w(G) = b$. By Theorems 1.2 and 1.4, every weak edge detour basis contains W and at least one vertex from each F_i ($1 \leq i \leq a$). Thus $dn_w(G) \geq (b - a) + a = b$. On the other hand, since the set $S_1 = W \cup \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_a\}$ is a weak edge detour set of G , it follows that $dn_w(G) \leq |S_1| = b$. Therefore $dn_w(G) = b$.

Next we show that $fdn_w(G) = a$. It is clear that W is the set of all weak edge detour vertices of G . Hence it follows from Theorem 2.11 that $fdn_w(G) \leq dn_w(G) - |W| = b - (b - a) = a$. Now, since $dn_w(G) = b$, it is easily seen that a set S is a weak edge detour basis of G if and only if S is of the form $S = W \cup \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_a\}$, where $y_i \in \{v_i, x_i\} \subseteq V(F_i)$ ($1 \leq i \leq a$). Let T be a subset of S with $|T| < a$. Then there is a vertex y_j ($1 \leq j \leq a$) such that $y_j \notin T$. Let $s_j \in \{v_j, x_j\} \subseteq V(F_j)$ distinct from y_j . Then $S' = (S - \{y_j\}) \cup \{s_j\}$ is a weak edge detour basis that contains T . Thus S is not the unique weak edge detour basis containing T . Thus $fdn_w(S) \geq a$. Since this is true for all weak edge detour basis of G , it follows that $fdn_w(G) \geq a$ and so $fdn_w(G) = a$. \square

Figure 5: G

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